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Life Farm, Fresh Fruit - Effects of Operator Training and Sprayer Adjustments on Agronomic Inputs

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Summary

Reducing the use of pesticides in fruit production is a major global societal challenge and is in line with the European *Green Deal* and EU Directive 2009/128/EC, demanding integrated pest management as well as with 2016/2031/EC, which requires that a proportionate and effective response to plant health threats is established through a combination of technological, ecological and institutional management. Still, pesticide overuse is wide spread and imprecise application causes serious health problems, dangerous pest resistances, and considerable negative effects for biodiversity, bee life, bystanders, and the ecosystem as a whole.

Addressing this serious problem, the *Life Farm, Fresh Fruit project (Life-F₃, LIFE18 ENV/ES/000349)* supported by the EU's funding instrument for environment and climate action, demonstrates in the case of a Spanish vineyard and a Portuguese olive plantation, that reductions of over 25 % of biocidal products and/or pesticides are possible through a.) readily available high-end sprayer technology, b.) precise spray equipment adaptation to the vegetation and c.) operator training for effective execution of spray jobs.

Key words: Integrated pest management, IPM, pesticide reduction, drift reduction, fuel savings, Smartomizer, EU LIFE Programme.

Introduction

According to the *World Health Organization* (WHO), low fruit and vegetable intake causes approximately 1.7 million deaths per year (WHO, 2019). At the same time, studies predict serious fruit shortages up to 2050, with the world population reaching 9 billion (FAO, 2009 and Grethe *et al.* 2011), while pests and diseases are responsible for 25 % to 40 % yield loss before harvest globally (FAO, 2020). Moreover, pesticide residues are the most important food-related concern for EU citizens (EUROB, 2010), and the *European Food Safety Authority* (EFSA) announced that more than 45 % of food products analysed (apples, head cabbage, lettuce, peaches, spinach, strawberries, tomatoes, barley, oats, wine grapes, swine fat, and milk) contain pesticide residues (EFSA, 2021).

Thus, reducing the use of pesticides in fruit production is a major global societal challenge and it is in line with European Directive 2009/128/EC, demanding *integrated pest management* (IPM) as well as with 2016/2031/EC, which requires that a proportionate and effective response to plant health threats is established through a combination of technological, ecological and institutional management. Still, pesticide overuse is wide spread and imprecise application causes serious health problems and dangerous pest resistances. Large parts of conventional spraying equipment are still highly inefficient. The size of the problem has been quantified in the three-year study *Save Spray*, directed by the *Valencian Institute of Agriculture Research* (IVIA), in collaboration with FEDE, the *University of Lleida*, and the *Polytechnical University of Catalonia* (UPC) (Molto *et al.*, 2012). The study revealed that 50% of *plant protection product* (PPP) do not reach the plants but are lost due to drift, run-off, and ground losses when using conventional spraying equipment. As a result, a large number of pesticides are found in ambient air (Coscolla *et al.*, 2013) contaminating the environment, with considerable negative effects for biodiversity, bee life, bystanders, and the ecosystem as a whole.

Addressing this serious environmental problem, the EU *Life-F₃* project demonstrates, in the case of the Spanish vineyard *Viñas del Vero* (VERO) and the Portuguese olive plantation *OUTEIRO Do Outeiro Sociedade Agricola, S.A.* (OUTEIRO), that reduction of over 25 % of *biocidal products and/or pesticides* is possible simply through the correct use of existing spraying equipment which is at the core of this study.

OUTEIRO is part of *Nutrifarms* (www.nutrifarms.pt), a world leader in high-quality olive oil production, with over 7 000 *hectares* (ha) of modern irrigated olive groves in southern Portugal (Alentejo) and Morocco (Marrakesh). Its *vision* is “to manage its farms and mills with the most innovative and sustainable techniques in order to obtain products of excellence”.

VERO (www.vinasdelvero.com) is an ISO9002 certified winery of international prestige, with over 700 ha and a yearly production capacity of 70 000 hectolitres, *i.e.* 5 million bottles. VERO’s varieties include Tempranillo, Moristel, Garnacha and Macabeo, Chardonnay, Gewürztraminer, Cabernet Sauvignon, Merlot and Pinot Noir. These are nursed and processed in line with VERO’s drive for “Quality, Sustainability and respect for the Environment”.

The spraying equipment under test at OUTEIRO and VERO includes an *in-cab tablet based operator guidance and proactive application error prevention system*, precise adaptation of the sprayers to vegetation mass (expressed in terms of *tree row volume* (TRV)), real time back office monitoring of application parameters, as well as the option to correct faulty treatments through partial re-treatment of selective areas if deemed necessary as introduced in (Garcerá *et al.*, 2018 and Berger *et al.*, 2019).

Reducing pesticides by over 25 % goes hand in hand with using 25 % less water to dissolve and transport these pesticides plus potential adjuvants. Further, a fine grain adaptation to the TRV means that the air to transport pesticide and water to the plant is reduced, which has a direct effect on fuel consumed by the tractor that is driving the air turbine. In FEDE’s high-end sprayer range, as

well in *John Deere* sprayers manufactured by FEDE, this means that the mean power consumption of the air turbine is reduced by over 55 % (from 37 kW for the baseline reference sprayer to 16 kW in the so called *Smartomizer H₃O*), which for standard tractors relates to over 4 L of diesel fuel saving per hour of operation. As a side effect from turbine re-design, noise contamination produced by the sprayers is reduced by 15 dBA with respect to baseline (Garcera *et al.*, 2018).

However, to gain the trust of end users, in *Life-F₃* a practical in-field approach is taken to demonstrate savings by running FEDE's *Smartomizer H₃O* and comparing results against existing baseline tracer sprayers on OUTEIRO's and VERO's.

Moreover, making most efficient use out of existing technology, requires educated dealer support staff who assists farmers during set-up and configuration as well as in their first steps putting the system to work in the field. Thus, dealer certification, following a *train-the-trainers approach*, is a very essential part of *Life-F₃* as detailed in Section "Materials and Methods".

Materials and Methods

Sprayer technology

Pesticide losses into the environment, be it via evaporation, air borne drift, ground losses or run-offs have devastating effects on biodiversity. Hence, the precision sprayers and digital services designed and produced by FEDE have several mechanisms to reduce pesticide losses.

Figure 1 shows a simplified conceptual presentation of FEDE's technology. Precise spray equipment adaptation to the vegetation mass TRV is performed before the application and real time back office monitoring of application parameters is implemented (Berger *et al.*, 2019).

Looking at Figure 1, it becomes apparent that *Life-F₃* material is much more than a sprayer. It is a whole speciality crop agricultural environment bringing digitalization and precision to 3D crops. It can be seen that sprayers with a FEDE developed *sprayer control system* (SCS) on the implement side connect via *Wi-Fi* with an *Android based terminal* in the tractor's cab (TAPP).

Figure 1: Top level *Life-F₃* technology deployment view.

The tractor carries also a *specialty crop gateway* (SCG) that guides the sprayer operator and connects tractor and sprayer via cellular modem to the Internet and from there to FEDE’s private Cloud, referred to as *Specialty Crops Platform* (SCP). Farmers and agronomic advisors have access to the *Specialty Crops Platform* via web *graphical user interfaces* (GUIs). This way, they can perform actions like sending prescriptions, or work orders to the sprayer operator, or monitoring results. Moreover, through this GUI, back office staff can post-process data. For example, it can automatically produce the farm book that records all plant protection product treatments and *interoperability* with other service providers is assured through an *application programming interfaces* (APIs).

Training for effective execution of spray jobs

Another important asset is an online learning platform, *Fede Academy* (Figure 2), that contains presentations, handbooks, but most importantly, a fine selection of short video tutorials, guiding farmers, operators, and dealers through all necessary steps.

Distance training and self-learning produced within *Life-F₃* and offered through the online learning platform *Fede Academy* has gained special importance during the COVID-19 lockdown, as it maximizes the impact of the implementation of *Life-F₃* technology mitigating even in a pandemic some problems related to displacement limitations.

As such, an only *training program* for farm owners, advisors, sprayer operators, and distributors has been established, as proper usage and maintenance of the equipment is indeed absolutely essential to sustainably obtain agronomic input savings.

Moreover, *Fede Academy* is also a handy tool for internal training within FEDE.

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Figure 2: *Fede Academy* Online learning Platform.

Objectives and success metrics

Life-F₃ has set out to:

1.) reduce the use of pesticides in fruit and olive production: Measures are to put FEDE's *Smartomizers H₃O* and digital services to pilot trials at VERO and OUTEIRO. The success metric is 25% reduction of pesticide usage with respect to standard application equipment currently in use on the demonstration plantations.

2.) reduce *greenhouse gas* (GHG) emissions produced in vine and olive production: Measures are to adapt FEDE's *Smartomizers H₃O* to field zone and plant conditions. Adaption lowers the amount of air used and, in the sequel, lowers the power consumed by the sprayer, reflected in lower tractor fuel consumption. Burning less diesel is directly related to the reduction of the GHGs *CO₂*, *CH₄* and *NO₂*, and is in *Life-F₃* calculated using the *Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (IPCC) guidelines (WHO, 2006). The success metric is 4 litres of diesel fuel reduction per hour in OUTEIRO's olive plantation (with axial fan air blast *Smartomizer H₃O*) and 1.7 litres per hour in VERO's vineyard (with air assisted side-by-side *Smartomizer H₃O*), both measured against the benchmark of currently used standard sprayers.

Data collection methodology

To demonstrate that *Smartomizers H₃O* actually achieve the above set objectives, farming partners VERO and OUTEIRO monitored fuel, water, and pesticide consumption, as well as the quality of spray distribution in the canopy over the growing seasons 2020 and 2021 for an on farm baseline sprayer and the respective *Smartomizer H₃O*.

With the aim to obtain comparable quality results the same work methodology was established at both the farming partners:

In VERO's case, the tests are carried out in the specific area of their farm (Figure 3). The area has a surface of 13 ha and was planted in 2006 with of Chardonnay variety. These 13 ha were split into two equal parts for both types of sprayers. The conventional sprayer worked in the blue area and the *Smartomizer H₃O* worked in the green area.

Figure 3. VERO's test areas.

Similarly, OUTEIRO's carried out tests on 314 ha of olive varieties, *Oliana* and *Arbequina*. Plots were distributed so that the reference sprayer and the *Smartomizer H₃O* worked on 157 ha each.

Results

Agronomic Input Savings in OUTEIRO's Olive Production

At OUTEIRO's farm *Herdade do Outeiro* the *Smartomizer H₃O* of type *M120 M2.0* as shown in Figure 4(a) is tested with a sprayer configuration that allows a sufficient spray droplet distribution as shown in Figure 4 (b).

Tests results achieved showed a reduction of spray volume by 17.65 % (from 850 L/ha to 700 L/ha), maintaining a coverage higher than 10 % in all sample points as shown in Figure 4 (b), where the App *SnapCard* (Gov. West. Australia, 2013) is used to determine the coverage on the water-sensitive paper.

Figure 4. (a) *Smartomizer H₃O* during tests in OUTEIRO's farm *Herdade do Outeiro*.
(b) Coverage measurement achieved with *Smartomizer H₃O*.

In addition to the 17.65 % PPP and spray water reduction achieved, work performance, measured in ha treated per hour, improved by around 26 % (from 2.25 ha/h to 3 ha/h) thanks to a tractor forward speed increment from 7.5 km/h to 9 km/h that becomes possible due to the fact that the *Smartomizer H₃O* requires less tractor power for the actual spraying action albeit at a comparable fuel consumption as compared to the reference sprayer working at 7.5 km/h. Thus, OUTEIRO staff not only spent less time spraying (with the associated labour cost savings) but also spent approximately 26% less fuel (recalling that tractor fuel consumption while spraying is measured as L/h).

Concluding, while significant positive impacts are achieved for the environment (17.65% PPP, and 26% GHG), there are also important economic savings from moving from the reference sprayer with a cost of 332 €/ha to the *Smartomizer H₃O* with a cost of 271.35 €/ha.

Agronomic Input Savings in VERO's Vine Production

FEDE's *Smartomizer H₃O* model *Tecnovid Qi M2.0* (Figure 5 (a)) is tested on the Chardonnay variety and is compared to a reference sprayer *Berthoud model Cruis'air Mega* at VERO's farm. Both sprayers are duly adjusted to the canopy taking the phenological state of the vineyard into account. A sample of spraying coverage of the *Smartomizer H₃O* tested with the help of water-sensitive paper is shown on Figure 5(b).

Figure 5. (a) *Smartomizer H₃O* tests at VERO's farm.
(b) Coverage test on water-sensitive paper by *Smartomizer H₃O*.

The spray volume (L/ha) of the *Smartomizer H₃O Tecnovid Qi* is reduced as shown in Table 1, which overall amounts to a PPP and spray water saving of 30 %.

Table 1. Spray volume in (L/ha) tested on VERO's farm with each type of sprayer.

Treatment	Spray volume (L/ha)										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
Berthoud Cruis'air	200	200	250	300	350	350	350	350	350	350	350
<i>Smartomizer H₃O</i>	155	155	195	210	225	225	225	225	225	225	225

Moreover, *Smartomizer H₃O* allowed to increase work performance (ha/h) by 18 % (from 4 ha/h to 4.7 ha/h). The performance increment is due to a tractor forward speed increase from 8.3 km/h to 8.7 km/h that becomes possible of less tractor horsepower consumption for the actual spraying job. Additionally, the fact of spray volume reduction influences to the performance as the spray tank needs to be filled less often, which reduces refilling overhead. In combination with large difference in the fuel consumption between the reference sprayer (around 15 L/h of diesel per hour) and the *Smartomizer H₃O* (around 8.5 L/h) allowed fuel savings of 52.6 %.

Concluding, apart from the significant positive environmental effects (30% PPP, and 52.6 % GHG reduction), the cost of treatment is reduced from 219 €/ha for the reference sprayer to 153.5 €/ha for the *Smartomizer H₃O*.

Contribution to EU LIFE KPIs

The EU monitors the impact of all *LIFE* projects through specific *key performance indicators* (KPIs) at the beginning and end of a project as well as three and five years after project end. As *Life-F₃* is currently mid-way through execution, Table 2 shows VERO's and OUTEIRO's EU *LIFE* KPI contributions so far.

Table 2. Contribution of the demo sites OUTEIRO (314 hectares) and VERO (700 hectares) to EU *LIFE* Programme KPIs.

Specific Context	Descriptor	Begin Value	Mid-term Value	Unit
Water used	Due to spray water saved	3 469	2 576	m ³ /year
Chemical released	Due to PPP saved	35.3	28.1	t/year
CO ₂ emissions	Due to diesel fuel saved	78.21	38.87	t/year
NO ₂ emissions	Due to diesel fuel saved	1.12	0.55	t/year
CH ₄ emissions	Due to diesel fuel saved	12.7	6.31	t/year

Discussion

Smartomizer H₃O achieve direct environmental benefits at the farms of VERO and OUTEIRO reducing spray volumes (water and pesticides) by 30 % and 17.65 %, respectively. It also reduces tractor diesel fuel consumption which consequently reduces greenhouse gases emissions up by 52.6 % and 26 %, at VERO and OUTEIRO, respectively.

In regards to social benefits, remote configuration of *Smartomizer H₃O*, as well as job traceability allows field job management from the home office, with less actual displacements, which in the sequel can render agricultural exploitations more pandemic resilient. Apart pesticide savings due to *Life-F₃* technology have a positive effect on human health.

Gaining through projects like *Life-F₃* trust among farmers for technology adoption help to overcome main hurdles when it comes to the roll-out and replication of disruptive precision farming innovation. Thus, *Life-F₃* has a clear focus on piloting and demonstration as well as on developing processes and methods that allow us to train any *Smartomizer H₃O* users, *i.e.*, clients, operators, advisors, and dealers.

Especially, dealer training is key as the role-out of *Life-F₃* digital technology requires knowledgeable support staff that serves customers in local language and is operational during office hours in the respective time zones around the globe. Therewith *Life-F₃* bridges the gap between research and development to widespread implementation of innovative solutions.

Moreover, with 7.2 tons of pesticides savings per year on the test farms so far (taking the difference between “Begin Value” and “Mid-term Value” in Table 2), *Life-F₃* demonstrates its potential to significantly contribute to the EU's Biodiversity Strategy, *i.e.*, to Target 1 to “Protect species and habitats” and Target 3 to “Achieve more sustainable agriculture and forestry”. Apart, *Life-F₃* promotes compliance of the EU's Sustainable Use directives 2009/128/EC, demanding integrated pest management and directive 2016/2031/EC demanding a proportionate and effective response to plant health threats through a combination of technological, ecological and institutional management. In fact, the development of cloud-based precision agriculture is the first step to mainstream IPM principles. Moreover, *Life-F₃* is fully aligned with the EU's *Ecodesign Working*

Plan 2016-2019, the EU Action Plan for the Circular Economy, and the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

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